

MODELLING THE THREE-POINT BENDING OF NOVEL BIOINSPIRED DENTAL CROWN COMPOSITES

U. Jargalsaikhan¹, H. Wan², N. Leung¹, B. Su², X. Song³, J. Hu⁴, T. Sui^{1*}
¹ Bioinspired Materials Group, Department of Mechanical Engineering Sciences, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey, UK,
² Biomaterials Engineering Group (bioMEG), Bristol Dental School, University of Bristol, Bristol, U.K.,
³ Department of Mechanical and Automation Engineering, Chinese University of Hong Kong, Shatin, Hong Kong, China,
⁴ Sente Software Ltd., 40 Occam Road, Surrey Technology Centre, Guildford, Surrey, UK
 * Corresponding author: tsui@surrey.ac.uk

1. Background

Dental CARIES: a Global Issue

Figure 1.1. Dental hard tissue loss, a. Sound enamel, b. Initial lesion, c and d. Extensive lesion [1].

Caries is the major cause of dental hard tissue damage and teeth loss. It is an **infectious, chronic** disease that has affected **millions** of people globally [2].

- **3.2 billion** people worldwide are affected by oral disease (2019) [2].
- **22 million** adults were seen by an NHS dentist in England (2018) [3].
- **9.7 million** treatment courses in one quarter of 2018-2019 [3].
- **20%** of ceramics used as top layers fail within the first 5 years of use [4].

Current Treatment Solutions

Figure 1.2. Commercial dental crown materials

Novel Dental Crown Materials Inspired by Nature

Figure 1.3 (a) Natural nacre. (b) Nacre layered structure acquired by SEM [5].

- Nature designs a perfect complex structure in living organisms on a **macro and nano-level**.
- The hierarchical structure of natural teeth is overly complex for our current manufacturing techniques.
- However, nacre (known as mother of pearl) has a simpler microstructure of **aragonite** platelets held together by **proteins** that provide good strength and fracture resistance [6].

2. Materials and Methodology

Bioinspired alumina (Al_2O_3) scaffolds were achieved by using a **cost-effective**, bi-directional freeze-casting technique. It was later densified, sintered and polymer infiltrated as described in [7].

The four different polymers used in this study are:

- Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)
- Urethane dimethacrylate/Triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (UDMA/TEGDMA)
- Polyurethane (PU)
- Epoxy.

Figure 2.1 The microstructure SEM images of Al_2O_3 composites with different polymer phases. (a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PMMA}$, (b) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{UDMA-TEGDMA}$, (c) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PU}$ and (d) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{epoxy}$.

Figure 2.2 A schematic diagram of the three-point bending test. (a) The geometry equivalent uniform structure model, (b) Bioinspired multi-layer structure, (c) 2D axisymmetric three-point bending boundary conditions used in FEM.

The FEM simulations were carried out using the commercial finite element software, ABAQUS® (version 6.4.2, 2018). Two types of models were proposed using the same finite element framework:

- Bioinspired multi-layer model
- Equivalent uniform structure model, without a layered architecture, to compare the stress distributions in the four composites.

Constant displacement of 0.7 mm applied on the top pin and 2D 4-node bilinear plane strain quadrilateral elements (CPE4R) were used to simulate the model.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

The present study focused on stress distributions in bioinspired multi-layer Al_2O_3 composites and compared them with an equivalent uniform structure model using 2D FEM modelling. The σ_{avg} in multi-layer models is lower than that of the equivalent uniform structure models.

In addition, polymer associated differences were identified in σ_{avg} . This modelling technique requires less computational memory along with faster convergence, meaning it can be beneficial in optimising polymer composition for further 3D modelling to investigate tri-axial stress state. Thus, it will develop better understanding on the mechanical performance of a novel, bioinspired, Al_2O_3 based dental crown material.

Acknowledgements

The EPSRC project (EP/S022813/1) "Understanding and enhancing the mechanical performance of bioinspired zirconia-based dental materials" is acknowledged for the funding support.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3.1 Principal stress distribution in equivalent uniform structure models of Al_2O_3 composites. The central region of the model magnified to show the stress concentration area. (a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PMMA}$, (b) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{UDMA-TEGDMA}$, (c) PU, (d) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{epoxy}$. The scale bar is in MPa. With insert image of high magnification of stress concentrated area.

The average stress (σ_{avg}) value was calculated from the central line nodes under the top pin. According to the statistical analysis, there was a statistically significant difference in σ_{avg} between equivalent uniform structure models and bioinspired multi-layer models ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure 3.2 Principal stress distribution in bioinspired multi-layer structure models of alumina-based composites. The central region of the model magnified to show the stress concentration area. (a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PMMA}$, (b) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{UDMA-TEGDMA}$, (c) PU, (d) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{epoxy}$. The scale bar is in MPa.

In each model, the differences between polymer components' σ_{avg} is minimal in equivalent uniform structure models, whereas it is significantly higher in bioinspired multi-layer models ($p \leq 0.05$). The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PMMA}$ composites displayed higher σ_{avg} than $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{UDMA-TEGDMA}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PU}$ composites ($p \leq 0.05$). However, a statistically significant difference was not found between the σ_{avg} of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PMMA}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{epoxy}$ composites ($p \leq 0.05$).

References

- Manu Rathee, Amit Sapra, Dental caries, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK551699/, accessed 10 June 2022.
- World Health Organization, "The World Oral Health Report 2003," *Community Dent. Oral Epidemiol.*, vol. 31 Suppl 1, pp. 3–23, 2003, doi: 10.1046/j.2003.com122.x.
- NHS, *NHS dental statistics frequency review 2019*, 2019.
- W. C. Wagner, T. M. Chu, "Biaxial flexural strength and indentation fracture toughness of three new dental core ceramics," *J. Prosthet. Dent.*, vol. 76, no. 2, pp. 140–144, Aug. 1996, doi: 10.1016/S0022-3913(96)90297-8.
- J. Peng *et al.*, "Inverse Nacre-like Epoxy-Graphene Layered Nanocomposites with Integration of High Toughness and Self-Monitoring," *Matter*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 220–232, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matt.2019.08.013.
- Barthelat F. Biomimetics for next generation materials. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*. 2007;365:2907-2919
- H. Wan, N. Leung, S. Algharibeh, T. Sui, Q. Liu, H. Peng and B. Su "Cost-effective fabrication of bio-inspired nacre-like composite materials with high strength and toughness," *Composites Part B Engineering*. Vol. 202, pp 108414, 2020.